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Guanidinium Like-Charge Ion Pairing and Oligoarginine Aggregation in Water by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, Cryo-Electron Microscopy, and Molecular Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

Like-charge pairing is a physical manifestation of the unique solvation properties of certain ion pairs in water. Water's high dielectric constant and related charge screening capability significantly influence the interaction between like-charged ions, with the possibility to transform it—in exceptional cases when noncovalent interactions are involved—from repulsion to attraction. Guanidinium cations (Gdm^+) represent a quintessential example of such like-charge pairing due to their specific geometry and electronic structure. In this work, we present experimental validation and quantification of $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ contact ion pairing in water utilizing nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy complemented by molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and density functional theory (DFT) calculations. The observed $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ interaction is attractive albeit weak—about $-0.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ —which aligns with theoretical estimation from MD simulations. We contrast the behavior of Gdm^+ with that of NH_4^+ cations, which exhibit no contact ion pairing in water. DFT calculations predict that the NMR chemical shift of Gdm^+ dimers is different than that of monomers, in agreement with NMR titration curves that display a nonlinear Langmuir-like behavior. Additionally, we conducted cryo-electron microscopy—to our knowledge, for the first time—on concentrated oligoarginines R_9 , which, unlike nona-lysines K_9 , exhibit aggregation in water. These results point to like charge pairing of the guanidinium side chain groups, as corroborated also by MD simulations and free energy calculations.

1 | Introduction

The contact like-charge pairing of ions in water is counterintuitive from the physical point of view since two positively or two negatively charged ions should repel each other according

to Coulomb's law. However, it has been suggested that certain like-charge ions in water attract each other instead [1–3]. This effect is enabled by the high dielectric constant of the environment (78.5 in water vs. 1 in the gas phase), attenuating the electrostatic repulsion energy at contact between two

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like-charge ions from $\sim 400 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in the gas phase to only several $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in water [4]. In exceptional cases, this residual repulsion is (over)compensated by attractive van der Waals and other interactions, resulting in net attraction [4].

Notably, contact like-charge ion-pairing in water has been predicted computationally for planar, quasi-aromatic guanidinium (Gdm^+) cations in numerous MD studies employing both empirical force fields (FFs) and electronic structure methods [3–6]. Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ pairing may be important in biological contexts since Gdm^+ is the side chain group of the essential amino acid arginine [7–9]. Close contacts of Gdm^+ moieties are observed in many protein structures [6], potentially regulating various protein functions [10].

On the experimental side, only a few studies currently exist in the literature predicting the Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ pairing in solution, such as X-ray spectroscopy of Gdm^+ ions [11], mass spectrometry studies of Gdm^+ water clusters [12], and electrophoretic mobility experiments of tetraarginines [13]. Also, the thermodynamic volumetric and activity data of Gdm^+ salts differ significantly from those of salts of simple spherical ions, indicating anomalies in Gdm^+ hydration and Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ interactions [14, 15]. In the biological context, the existence of like-charge Gdm^+ -containing aggregates has been suggested by small angle X-ray spectroscopy (SAXS) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) experiments for deca-arginines (R_{10}) in water [16]. There is also an indirect indication of nona-arginine (R_9) aggregation at phospholipid bilayers, as evidenced by fluorescence assays at supported lipid bilayers [17].

A peek into the molecular origins of the like-charge ion pairs has been provided by computational studies, employing both electronic structure methods [5, 6] and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with empirical FFs [3, 5, 18]. Namely, attraction between Gdm^+ ions is observed when dispersion interactions are included, suggesting that the van der Waals forces—uniquely strong for Gdm^+ due to its very specific quasi-aromatic electronic structure [4, 5, 18]—play a key role in the total energy balance. Conspicuously, almost all FFs used in classical MD simulations predict Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ like-charge pairing, albeit with different strengths due to favorable van der Waals parameters. In contrast, the interaction between NH_4^+ ions (which serve as a mimic of the lysine side chain), as well as lysine-rich peptides, leads to mutual repulsion in the above studies employing various levels of theory.

In this work, we focus on two examples of the Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ like-charge ion pairing by a synergistic combination of two experimental techniques supported by MD simulations. First, we applied NMR titration experiments complemented with FF MD simulations and density functional theory (DFT) calculations of NMR shifts, establishing the experimental free energy of Gdm^+ – Gdm^+ attraction in water for the first time. Second, we expanded the existing experimental data on the interaction of arginine-rich peptides in water, providing conclusive evidence of R_9 aggregation by cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM), supported by FF MD simulations.

2 | Methods

2.1 | Chemicals

Guanidinium chloride, ammonium chloride, sodium chloride, and calcium chloride were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich (St. Louis, MO) with 99% purity. H-(Lys)₉-OH (K_9), and H-(Arg)₉-OH (R_9) were synthesized by solid-phase peptide synthesis (SPPS) on PS3 peptide synthesizer (Gyros Protein Technologies, USA) using standard Fmoc chemistry protocols, HBTU coupling reagents, and 2-chlorotrityl chloride resin support (0.1 mmol scale and 10 equivalent amino acid excess). Side-chain-protected peptides were cleaved off the resin with a mixture of acetic acid/2,2,2-trifluoroethanol/dichloromethane (1:1:3) for 2 h at room temperature. The resin was filtered off, reagents and solvents were evaporated to dryness, and residues were treated with the mixture of water/trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)/triisopropylsilane (95:2.5:2:5). The cleaved and deprotected peptides were lyophilized and purified by RP HPLC (Vydac 218TP101522 column) using methanol and water with 0.05% TFA as solvents. The purity was assessed by analytical RP-HPLC (Vydac 218TP54 column) and liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry (LC/MS, Agilent Technologies 6230 ToF LC/MS). The mass was confirmed by MALDI-ToF MS: H-(Lys)₉-OH $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ 1171.9; H-(Arg)₉-OH $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ 1423.9.

2.2 | Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Experiments

In order to study specific ion–ion interactions by NMR, we have eliminated the variation in the mean-field electrostatic screening effects by performing our experiments at a constant ionic strength. When experiments are conducted in neat water, the increase of GdmCl concentration changes the ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR shifts of the Gdm^+ proton and carbon atoms, respectively, as illustrated in Figure S1. Therefore, we prepared a dilution series with decreasing concentrations of GdmCl and NH_4Cl , keeping constant ionic strength by adding NaCl in the appropriate amount. The samples were prepared simultaneously to protect them from solvent evaporation, which could negatively affect the salt concentration. 3.1 and 3 M solutions of GdmCl and NH_4Cl , as well as 6 M GdmCl were prepared in $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{D}_2\text{O}$ mixture (volume ratio 9:1) and diluted by 3 M or 6 M NaCl solution in $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{D}_2\text{O}$ mixture, respectively. For both salt concentrations, chemical shifts were referenced to an internal standard *t*-BuOH (1.24 ppm for ^1H and 30.29 ppm for ^{13}C , respectively). The exception to this is the supplementary measurements in neat water, where chemical shifts were referenced to nitromethane as an external standard (4.40 ppm for ^1H and 63.23 ppm for ^{13}C , respectively). The NMR spectra were recorded on a 500 MHz spectrometer (^1H at 500 MHz, ^{13}C at 125.7 MHz) at room temperature (298 K).

2.3 | Cryo-Electron Microscopy Experiments

Cryo-EM samples of concentrated peptide solutions were prepared on either 300 mesh 2/2 Quantifoil or C-flat EM grids (Electron Microscopy Sciences, USA), on which 10 nm protein A-conjugated colloidal gold particles (Au–NP) were preadsorbed (Aurion, the Netherlands). Au–NP adsorbed grids were then

glow-discharged (30 s, 40 mA) in a Quorum GLOQUBE Plus system. An aliquot (3.0 μL) of either (i) 100 mM solution of nona-arginine (R_9) or nona-lysine (K_9) in 150 mM NaCl with added 100 mM CaCl_2 prior to sample freezing or (ii) 150 mM NaCl with added 100 mM CaCl_2 prior to sample freezing was applied to the carbon side of EM grids, and subsequently blotted for 2.0 s at blot force -7 and plunge-frozen into the precooled liquid ethane with a Vitrobot Mark IV (FEI, USA).

Cryo-electron micrographs of vitrified samples were collected using a transmission electron microscope JEOL JEM-2100PLUS (JEOL, Japan) equipped with a TemCam-XF416(ES) (TVIPS, Germany) camera, using an Elsa cryo-transfer holder model 698 (Gatan), at accelerating voltage of 200 keV. Grid mapping and image acquisition were performed using SerialEM software [19] at a nominal magnification of $80\times$ and $2500\times$, respectively. High-magnification images were recorded at $60,000\times$ nominal magnification (0.194 nm pixel size) with a $-10\mu\text{m}$ defocus value. To minimize radiation damage during image acquisition, the low-dose mode in SerialEM software was used, and the electron dose was kept below $100\text{ e}^-/\text{\AA}^2$.

Each high-magnification image of the vitrified samples was first converted to an 8-bit format and binned by 4 to enhance feature recognition. Subsequently, a 250-pixel size square region was selected from each image, the corresponding fast Fourier transform (FFT) was calculated using the respective command in Fiji software [20], and the normalized radial profile of the FFT power spectra was then measured using Radial Profile Angle plugin of Fiji. In addition, each selected image region was binarized using the center of the gray-level histogram as the threshold, and the resulting spatial autocorrelation function (ACF) was calculated using a MATLAB script.

2.4 | Electronic Structure Calculations

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations for the carbon-NMR chemical shifts were performed using the single point Gauge-Independent Atomic Orbital (GIAO) method with the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ basis set at the B3LYP-D3/cc-pVDZ optimized geometry (denoted as B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3/cc-pVDZ). The calculations were carried out on a $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer hydrated with 12 water molecules and compared to a Gdm^+ monomer hydrated with 6 water molecules. Additionally, the levels of theory B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3/aug-cc-pVDZ and B3LYP/6-311++G(2d,p)//B3LYP-D3/6-311+G(d,p), as well as the semi-experimental chemical shift calculation approach [21], were tested for the same system, see Table S1 for a full summary. NH_4^+ dimers—prepared as hydrated monomers with 4 water molecules per each and calculated at the same level of theory—were found unstable and dissociated, resulting in a formation of solvent-separated ion-pair instead, Figure S4. Calculated carbon-NMR shifts were subtracted from the reference carbon-NMR shift tetra-methyl silane (TMS) at the same level of theory. Additionally, carbon-NMR shift calculations were performed with the polarizable continuum model (PCM) at B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ//B3LYP-D3/aug-cc-pVDZ level of theory for $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimers [22, 23]. The carbon-NMR shifts were also calculated for the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimers with the increasing of the central

carbon distance keeping the stacked ion conformation, from 2.9 to 5.5 \AA in order to determine the cut-off distance beyond which the carbon-NMR shift remains relatively constant, Figure S5. The Grimme empirical dispersion correction was used for geometry optimizations of microhydrated clusters at the B3LYP level of theory [24]. All DFT calculations are performed with the Gaussian16 suite of codes [25].

2.5 | Molecular Dynamics Simulations

All-atom MD simulations were designed to resemble the composition of aqueous solutions used in the NMR and cryo-EM experiments and provide direct atomistic insights into the studied phenomena.

To resemble NMR systems, 400 GdmCl and 330 NH_4Cl ion pairs were dissolved in 5550 water molecules to achieve the desired concentration of $\sim 3\text{ M}$. Systems with lower GdmCl and NH_4Cl concentrations were prepared by adjusting the amount of Gdm^+ to [10, 25, 50, 100, 200] or NH_4^+ to [10, 20, 40, 80, 160] and adding the corresponding amount of sodium cations to have a total of 400 and 330 ion pairs, respectively. Similarly, 1100 GdmCl ion pairs were dissolved in 5500 water molecules to achieve $\sim 6.0\text{ M}$ concentration, and [50, 100, 200, 400, 800] Gdm^+ with added sodium were used to create lower concentrations. Thus, the total ionic strength of the solutions was always kept constant, as in the experiments. Three different FFs were tested for GdmCl/NaCl systems: Kirkwood–Buff (KB) FF [26], which does not predict $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ pairing; the updated version of KB model (KB2) that introduces $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ pairing into the original model [27]; and prosECCo75 model [28]—the CHARMM36 [29] derivative that incorporates the electronic polarization via charge scaling [30] and also suggests $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ pairing. For $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}/\text{NaCl}$ simulations, only the prosECCo75 model was used. The simulations were 500 ns long, with the first 100 ns omitted from all analyses.

Additional simulations were performed to evaluate the effect of the solvent on ion pairing. Specifically, 100 ns simulations of 0.5 M GdmCl (34 molecules, modeled using KB2 FF) were performed in methanol (2000 molecules) and ethanol (1500 molecules), while 200 ns simulations were carried out in water (4500 molecules).

For comparison with the cryo-EM data, both biased and unbiased MD simulations were conducted for aqueous solutions of R_9 and K_9 peptides. Only the prosECCo75 FF was employed for these simulations. First, free energy MD simulations were performed using the accelerated weight histogram (AWH) method with multiwalker sampling [31]. In each simulation, only two peptides (either R_9 or K_9) were present. Two ionic conditions were examined: one with 18 chloride counterions and another with chloride counterions and additional 104 CaCl_2 and 156 NaCl ion pairs, corresponding to ionic concentrations of 100 and 150 mM, respectively. The latter condition resembles the ionic environment used in the cryo-EM experiments. Each simulation system comprised 55,653 water molecules for the R_9 systems and 55,669 water molecules for the K_9 systems. The reaction coordinate for the free energy calculations was defined as the center-of-mass distance between the two peptides, sampled over a range

from 0.2 to 5.5 nm. Free energy profiles were generated using eight walkers, each initialized from configurations with peptide–peptide distances of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 4, and 5 nm, respectively. These initial configurations were extracted from a preliminary AWH simulation performed on the systems containing additional ions and conducted with a single walker. For AWH simulations involving only counterions, the extra ions were removed from the initial configurations. All free energy profiles were corrected for volume entropy effects [32] ($+2k_{\text{B}}T \ln(r)$) and subsequently shifted to zero at the largest distances, where peptide interactions are negligible. For all AWH calculations, the target distribution was set to be uniform. The initial diffusion constant was set to $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ nm}^2 \cdot \text{ps}$, and the initial error estimate was $10 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. The umbrella potential was applied with a force constant of $100,000 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{nm}^{-2}$.

Two independent AWH runs were carried out for each system. In the first set of runs, we used a looser (“covering”) criterion for exiting the initial (exploration) phase before entering the final stage, see Ref. [31] and the GROMACS manual for details. In this case, a single “covering” of the reaction coordinate is reached as soon as the reaction coordinate is *collectively* traversed by all walkers. This behavior is achieved by setting the so-called “cover diameter” to zero. The growth factor γ for the exponential phase was equal to 3 in these simulations. In the second set, a stricter criterion was enforced, which required that at least one walker sampled the entire reaction coordinate independently. In these runs, the cover diameter was set to 5.3 nm (i.e., the full length of the sampling interval), and the growth factor was set to 2. As a result, the initial exploration phase finished relatively quickly with the looser criterion ($\sim 0.5\text{--}1.5 \mu\text{s}$ of collective simulated time), whereas it took significantly longer with the stricter criterion ($\sim 4 \mu\text{s}$ for the K_9 systems, $\sim 8 \mu\text{s}$ for the R_9 system with excess ions, and was not achieved for the R_9 system with only counterions). The total AWH simulation time was: (i) for all K_9 -containing simulations and the R_9 simulations using the looser criterion, 625 ns per walker (an aggregate simulation time of $5 \mu\text{s}$ per energy profile, 8 walkers \times 625 ns); (ii) for the R_9 system with excess ions and the stricter criterion, $1.5 \mu\text{s}$ per walker (total $12 \mu\text{s}$); (iii) for the R_9 system with only counterions and the stricter criterion, $2 \mu\text{s}$ per walker (total $16 \mu\text{s}$). The reported free energy profiles are the averages obtained from the two runs, shown together with their corresponding standard deviations. Additional technical details of the AWH method are available in the original publication [31].

Next, we employed unbiased MD simulations to investigate how peptide concentration influences peptide interactions in aqueous solutions. Specifically, simulations were performed at two different peptide concentrations and under various ionic strengths. 6 and 16 peptide molecules (R_9 or K_9), corresponding to concentrations of approximately 20 and 50 mM, were solvated in aqueous solutions containing either no salt (apart from chloride counterions necessary to neutralize the positive net charge of the peptides), 130 mM NaCl, or 130 mM CaCl_2 . All simulation systems contained 15,856 water molecules. The proECCo75 FF was employed for these simulations. These simulations were $2 \mu\text{s}$ long, with the first 500 ns omitted from the analysis.

All MD simulations were performed using a leap-frog integrator with a time step of 2 fs in GROMACS engine [33]. We adopted

simulation protocols in accord with previously used and recommended for the corresponding FFs. Buffered Verlet lists [34] were used to keep track of atomic neighbors. The input cutoff for short-range electrostatic interactions was set to 1.2 nm (proECCo75) or 1 nm (KB and KB2). Long-range electrostatics was treated using smooth particle mesh Ewald (PME) algorithm [35]. The cutoff for Lennard–Jones interactions was set to 1.2 nm with the forces switched to zero starting at a distance of 1.0 nm [36] (proECCo75) or simply set to 1.0 nm (KB and KB2). The temperatures of 300 K (for the GdmCl and NH_4Cl solutions) and 310 K (for R_9 and K_9 solutions) were maintained by the Nosé–Hoover thermostat [37, 38] with a coupling time constant of 1 ps (proECCo75) or v-rescale thermostat [39] with a coupling time of 0.1 ps (KB and KB2). The Parrinello–Rahman barostat [40] with a coupling time constant of 5 ps (proECCo75) or 2 ps (KB and KB2) and compressibility of $4.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ bar}^{-1}$ was maintaining the pressure of 1 bar. Water was simulated as a CHARMM-specific TIP3P model [41, 42] (proECCo75) or SPC/E model [43] (KB and KB2). Methanol and ethanol were modeled using the OPLS/AA FF [44]. The corresponding NaCl models were used in combination with each FF, namely KB sodium and chloride ions [45] and proECCo75 “Na_s”, “Ca_s”, and “Cl_2s” (<https://gitlab.com/sparkly/prosecco/proECCo75>). Bonds in solute molecules involving hydrogen atoms were constrained using P-LINCS [46, 47], whereas the geometry of water was constrained using SETTLE [48]. In the case of KB simulations, all other covalent bonds were also constrained, following the original simulation protocol [26].

The simulation input files and trajectories for the GdmCl/NaCl and NH_4Cl /NaCl systems, as well as the AWH simulation input files and trajectories for the R_9 and K_9 systems (including peptide topologies also used in unbiased MD simulations of peptides), are available online in the Zenodo repository at DOIs 10.5281/zenodo.17775423 and 10.5281/zenodo.17776016.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Like-Charge Pairing of Gdm^+ Ions in Water

Figure 1A shows the experimental NMR chemical shifts with increasing Gdm^+ and NH_4^+ concentrations in GdmCl and NH_4Cl solutions, respectively. The experiments were performed at a constant ionic strength (i.e., at constant electrostatic screening of studied solutions) of approximately 3 M, which was imperative for accurate free energy determination of ion-specific $\text{Gdm}^+ \text{--} \text{Gdm}^+$ pairing [49]. Note that the approach of Gdm^+/Na^+ titration has previously been demonstrated to be successful in measuring the electrophoretic mobility of GdmCl solutions [13].

The nonlinear change in the observed ^1H NMR chemical shift in GdmCl solutions points to cation–cation binding. It is important to note that the effect cannot be attributed to $\text{Gdm}^+ \text{--} \text{Cl}^-$ pairing, which is essentially linearly dependent on concentration. This follows from the corresponding MD simulations radial distribution functions (RDFs) (Figure S6), showing nearly identical profiles across all tested concentrations. The measured difference $\Delta\delta$ in ^1H NMR shift can be used to characterize and quantify the energetics of binding by calculating the dissociation constant K_d

FIGURE 1 | (A) The concentration dependence of ^1H NMR chemical shift on the Gdm^+ or NH_4^+ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M is maintained by adding NaCl. (B) The like-charge pairing of the Gdm^+ cations as a function of Gdm^+ concentration in an aqueous solution, where a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M is maintained by adding NaCl. Data for the three MD force fields are compared: prosECCo75 and KB2 models show nonlinear behavior and, at the same time, capture contact ion $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ pairing, while KB model shows the linear behavior and does not capture contact ion $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ pairing. The standard deviation calculated by dividing the analysis into five equal time intervals does not exceed 0.3% (smaller than the data symbols) and is therefore not shown. The blue inset rectangle exemplifies $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ contact ion pairing from MD simulations using the prosECCo75 force field. NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; MD, molecular dynamics.

[50, 51]. The dependence of $\Delta\delta$ on Gdm^+ concentration follows a Langmuir isotherm, which can be fitted as:

$$\Delta\delta = \delta - \delta_0 = c \cdot A + \frac{\Delta\delta_{\max} \cdot c}{K_d + c}, \quad (1)$$

where A is a linear constant with units of chemical shift per molar concentration and $\Delta\delta_{\max}$ is the maximum change in chemical shift observed for the nonlinear portion of the curve at saturation.

We calculated the dissociation constant K_d for 3 M GdmCl solution to be ~ 0.8 M. Thus, Gdm^+ ions form a weakly stabilized contact ion pair in a solution of a 3 M ionic strength. The dissociation constant can be converted to the free energy of binding using the formula $\Delta G_b = -kT \ln K_b$, where $K_b = K_d^{-1}$

is the binding constant. Using this approach, we calculated the binding free energy of Gdm^+ ions to be approximately $-0.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at room temperature.

This finding provides the first experimental quantification of $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ contact ion pairing strength in aqueous solutions. In the solution of 6 M ionic strength, the like-charge pairing is stronger, which is expected since the higher ionic strength further attenuates the like charge electrostatic repulsion. This behavior is illustrated in Figure S2, where a nonlinear increase in ^1H NMR shift leads to an estimate of ΔG_b of $-3.0 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

Finally, as a negative control, we examined the NH_4Cl system where MD simulations predict no like-charge pairing [5, 6]. The measured ^1H NMR chemical shifts for the NH_4Cl solution at a constant ionic strength of 3 M exhibit no discernible trend, Figure 1A. This behavior is qualitatively different from the GdmCl experiments, indicating the absence of self-attraction for NH_4^+ ions in water. The slight decrease in the ^1H NMR chemical shift at lower concentrations is within the error bars, as the NMR signal is much broader than that of GdmCl (Figure S3), leading to a larger uncertainty.

Since the experimental NMR measurements cannot provide all the molecular details of the like-charge ion pairing, we performed MD simulations of the investigated systems. We modeled systems with varying concentrations of GdmCl and NH_4Cl , maintaining constant ionic strengths of approximately 3 M or 6 M by adding the appropriate amount of NaCl (see Section 2 for details). Ion pairing was quantified using two different distance cutoffs. The first cutoff was set at 3.9 \AA for C_z-C_z and 4.9 \AA for N_z-N_z in GdmCl and NH_4Cl , respectively. These values represent the maxima in the corresponding RDFs, Figure S7. The second cutoff of 4.5 \AA was applied to both systems and derived from NMR chemical shift PCM/GIAO calculations on the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer (see Section 2). The calculated ^{13}C NMR shift does not significantly change beyond a distance of 4.5 \AA between guanidinium carbons, see Figure S4. Therefore, we presume that beyond this cutoff, the Gdm^+ cations do not “feel” each other in the NMR experiments. This observation can also be extended to the interpretation of ^1H NMR experiments [52]. Therefore, the data calculated with the cutoff of 4.5 \AA are reported in the main text.

Our MD data, summarized in Figure 1B, show the calculated contact probability as a function of Gdm^+ concentration in GdmCl solutions at a constant ionic strength of ~ 3 M. Notably, two of the three FFs examined—KB2 and prosECCo75—exhibit a nonlinear trend that aligns with the NMR experiments. This trend indicates significant binding between Gdm^+ cations, with prosECCo75 showing slightly stronger attractive interactions. Importantly, only these two FFs capture the contact ion pairing of Gdm^+ cations, as shown in the inset of Figure 1B and the representative RDFs in Figure S7. In contrast, the KB model exhibits a linear trend, which indicates a lack of binding between Gdm^+ cations for this FFs. Similarly, the data for NH_4Cl solutions reveal an exclusively linear trend with increasing NH_4^+ concentration, Figure S9. All these conclusions hold true across both concentrations and cutoffs used to distinguish contact ion pairing, Figures S9 and S10.

The RDFs shown in Figure S7 can also be converted into the potentials of mean force, which provide an estimate of the binding free energy ΔG_b between a pair of Gdm^+ ions, Figure S8. Using RDFs derived from MD simulations of ~ 3 M GdmCl solution, the estimated ΔG_b from the energy minima is found to be -1.1 and -0.6 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for the proECCo75 and KB2 models, respectively, Table S2, which is in accord with our experimental NMR data.

We also compared the experimental NMR results with DFT calculations of GIAO NMR chemical shifts for optimized microhydrated Gdm^+ clusters, Figure S4. Specifically, we calculated the ^{13}C NMR chemical shift for a $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ dimer hydrated with 12 water molecules and compared it to that of a Gdm^+ monomer hydrated with 6 water molecules at various levels of theory. In all cases, the ^{13}C NMR shift of the dimer was consistently lower than that of the monomer, with differences ranging from 0.8 to 1.4 ppm, Table S1, as observed in the literature for benzene dimer [53]. The computational prediction that the ^{13}C NMR chemical shift difference between monomer and dimer is also experimentally validated. In addition, ^{13}C NMR experiments for GdmCl in 6 M ionic strength solutions demonstrate a nonlinear behavior of the chemical shift with increasing GdmCl concentration, similar to the ^1H NMR experiments, as shown in Figure S2. The estimated ΔG_b from the experimental ^{13}C NMR data is -3.7 $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, which is consistent with the experimental ^1H NMR data.

Previous simulations using PCM continuum models have shown that by decreasing the dielectric constant, the stability of the Gdm^+ dimer also decreases [4]. In particular, with $\epsilon = 20$, the cluster remains thermodynamically stable ($\Delta G_b \sim -2$ $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). However, when using $\epsilon = 4$, the dimer is thermodynamically unstable, with $\Delta G_b \sim 40$ $\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. To reassess the previous results obtained at the PCM continuum-level theory, which does not account for explicit solvent, we performed MD simulations of 0.5 M GdmCl in methanol and ethanol. The analysis of the results, as seen in 3D volumetric maps, Figure S11, clearly shows that, for ethanol and methanol, like-charged Gdm^+ pairs are not observed, and the Gdm^+ ions are instead found in the Gdm^+ plane being bridged by Cl^- anions, instead of in close contact on top of it, as is the case in water. This behavior is not only due to the decreased dielectric constant, but also to the inability of methanol and ethanol to form a robust hydrogen-bonding network around Gdm^+ dimer and to bridge individual Gdm^+ ions. In contrast, water has this ability, in turn stabilizing the dimer, as discussed in detail previously [5] and shown here in Figure S4 for Gdm^+ dimer in water. We also observe that the ethyl or methyl group has a non-negligible density above and below the Gdm^+ ion (Figure S11). In contrast, in an aqueous solution, this position is occupied by another Gdm^+ ion in close contact. These results are further corroborated by RDFs (Figure S12), which show the absence of the peak corresponding to the $\text{Gdm}^+-\text{Gdm}^+$ contact ion pairing in methanol and ethanol.

3.2 | Like-Charge Pairing of Oligoarginines in Water

To further experimentally address guanidinium-based ion pairing, we investigated the aggregation of biologically relevant oligopeptides in water using cryo-EM, comparing the behavior of guanidinium-containing nona-arginine R_9 with ammonium-

containing nona-lysine K_9 . The rationale behind this choice is that R_9 peptides are widely used as cell-penetrating peptides, with their aggregation properties in bulk being relevant for their translocation efficiency [17, 54].

Cryo-EM is often utilized to resolve protein structures or to image self-assembling systems such as lipid membranes and organic or metallic nanoparticles. Nevertheless, it can also visualize solutions of nanoscopic molecules [55], as demonstrated with heavy atom nanocrystals [56] and surfactant micelles [57]. Images of unstructured systems, such as peptides in solution, often exhibit low contrast due to the small size and composition differences compared to the surrounding bulk amorphous ice [57, 58], which limits the obtainable information. Here, to enhance the contrast and thus effectively assess differences in aggregation of different peptides, we modulated the microscope contrast transfer function (CTF) by shifting the image defocus to large values (-10 μm). By acquiring images at high defocus values, the signal from low spatial frequencies (i.e., lower resolution information) is increased, thus enhancing the contrast [59, 60]. This approach allows us to visualize features that would otherwise be difficult to identify. However, it should be noted that high-frequency/high-resolution information is significantly reduced with this method.

To maintain proper vitrification of the samples into glassy ice, the peptide concentration was maintained at 100 mM, while aggregation and clustering were enhanced by increasing the ionic strength of the buffer via the addition of 100 mM CaCl_2 , as observed in the earlier studies [61], and which are in line with the general salting-out effect [62]. The cryo-EM images of the two peptide solutions and buffer control show distinctly different patterns and features, visible in both grayscale and binarized images, see Figure 2. The R_9 peptide solution displays characteristic high density and spatial clustering of the signal; the K_9 peptide solution, while showing similar density to R_9 samples, possesses negligible features or clusters, and is more comparable to solvent-only images. While the high image density arises from the high concentration and charge of the peptides (since both R_9 and K_9 have the same total charge), the differences in spatial features are likely due to differences in peptide behavior in solution. The spatial clustering of similar gray-value pixels observed for nona-arginine resembles previously reported images of surfactant micelles [57], suggesting the presence of nanometric objects in the solution.

The two-dimensional FFT power spectra of the respective images further underscore the differences between the two peptide solutions. The R_9 solution displays a strong low-frequency signal and a second Thon ring [63], characteristic of significantly contrasted features within the images. Conversely, the K_9 solution shows lower intensity in the low spatial-frequency region and no second Thon ring, in line with the density observed in the images and fewer features or clusters. Comparing these images with those obtained from buffer-only samples (150 mM NaCl and 100 mM CaCl_2 , see Figure 2) reveals that the signal from the K_9 peptide solution is close to that of a peptide-free solution.

The analysis of the radial profiles of the respective FFT power spectra (Figure 3A) confirms that R_9 displays an enhanced signal at 0.16 nm^{-1} , corresponding to the first Thon ring, with an additional peak located at 0.41 nm^{-1} . In contrast, the FFT of

FIGURE 2 | Representative cryo-EM images of 100 mM R₉ (top, blue) and K₉ (mid, red) in 150 mM NaCl and 100 mM CaCl₂ aqueous buffer, as well as buffer-only (bottom, gray), along with their corresponding binarized images used for autocorrelation function calculations. The images display distinct differences in the spatial distribution of the intensity signals. The R₉ peptide solution exhibits clusters of pixels with the same gray values, while the K₉ peptide solution has a more diffuse distribution. Buffer-only images display much less features or clustering. Calculation of the median FFT from all replicates ($n = 205$ for R₉, $n = 152$ for K₉, and $n = 141$ for buffer-only) confirms significant differences between the two peptides, as well as peptide-free (buffer only) systems. The first (yellow) and second (purple) Thon rings are outlined in dashed colored circles on the FFT images. The scale bar for the cryo-EM images is 50 nm. EM, Electron microscopy; FFT, fast Fourier transform.

K₉ images show only a single Thon ring located at 0.13 nm^{-1} without any additional Thon rings present. Buffer-only radial profiles do not display any clear peak or Thon ring. While both R₉ and K₉ solutions exhibit a first Thon ring, comparison of their median radial profiles and the median absolute deviation (MAD) of the FFT distribution clearly shows differences between the two samples (Figure 3B). While at low wavenumber ($0.01\text{--}0.03 \text{ nm}^{-1}$) the two profiles largely overlap. In the region of $0.04\text{--}0.3 \text{ nm}^{-1}$, where the first Thon ring peak for both peptides occurs, the two distributions do not overlap, in line with differences in the FFT images (Figure 2); in addition, the R₉ Thon ring is shifted toward compared to K₉. At larger wavenumbers ($0.4\text{--}2 \text{ nm}^{-1}$) the two distributions mostly overlap, with the exception of the

R₉ secondary peak (corresponding to the second Thon ring) that is absent in K₉ and where the median and MAD distribution show a separation between the two peptides. When compared to the FFT of buffer-only images, the distinct first and second peaks in the R₉, which are absent in the buffer-only solutions (Figure S13A), indicate that the observed spatial clustering is a unique characteristic of the R₉ images. In addition, it is evident that the K₉ power spectra mostly overlap with those of peptide-free samples, Figure 3A and S13B, suggesting the absence of significant features in these images.

Analyzing the spatial ACF of the images further supports these findings, as the median ACF profile for R₉ distinctly differs from

FIGURE 3 | (A,B) Radial profiles derived from FFT power spectra images, showing a significantly different spatial signal distribution for R₉ (blue) compared to K₉ (red). (A) presents the median profiles, comparing them to the peptide-free (buffer-only, gray) system. (B) displays both the median and median absolute deviation (MAD) for the R₉ and K₉ systems only. (C,D) Spatial autocorrelation function curves calculated from cryo-EM images, representing the correlation of grayscale values as a function of pixel distance from each pixel (pixel size is 0.194 nm) for R₉ (blue) and K₉ (red) systems. (C) presents the median curves comparing them to the peptide-free (buffer-only, gray) system. (D) shows both the median and median absolute deviation for the R₉ and K₉ systems only. R₉ shows strong positive correlation (same gray values) at short pixel distances, followed by pronounced anticorrelation (opposite gray values), and ultimately a stochastic distribution at longer distances (tail baseline), altogether suggesting the presence of clusters. In contrast, the K₉ (red) data show a rapid decay to stochastic values, indicating minimal spatial correlation. Data are calculated from $n = 205$ frames for R₉, $n = 152$ frames for K₉, and $n = 141$ frames for buffer-only systems. FFT, fast Fourier transform.

both the K₉ and peptide-free systems (Figure 3C). Specifically, while the gray-value correlation for K₉ rapidly decays to no correlation after three neighboring pixels, with minimal anticorrelation (i.e., negative ACF values), R₉ signal remains correlated for approximately five pixels and subsequently exhibits strong anticorrelation (opposite gray values), as seen in Figure 3D. Moreover, the two peptide ACF profiles show no overlap in the 1–20 pixel region, with clear separation between R₉ and K₉ in both short-range positive correlation (1–5 pixels) and medium-range negative correlation (5–10 pixels).

Comparing the ACF curves of the peptides solutions with those of the buffer-only images further confirms that K₉ more closely resembles a peptide-free scenario, Figure S13C and S13D. While our analysis does not enable precise determination of cluster sizes due to resolution loss caused by high defocus during acquisition, it nevertheless demonstrates that the presence of peptides with guanidinium moieties in the side chains significantly promotes

aggregation/clustering compared to those with ammonium side chain groups.

To further corroborate the cryo-EM findings, we conducted MD simulations of R₉ and K₉ peptides in aqueous solutions. First, we obtained estimates of the peptide–peptide interaction free energy using AWH simulations with only two peptide molecules present in the system. As shown in Figure 4A, the free energy profiles reveal that only R₉ peptide pairs exhibit a negative (i.e., favorable) binding free energy, and this is observed only when a sufficient concentration of ions is present, which actually represents our cryo-EM conditions. This indicates that R₉ peptides can have a stable binding configuration under conditions that more closely resemble biological environments, where there are sufficient amounts of salt ions and other charged species present. When only counterions are available, R₉ peptides display local energy minima along the free energy curve; nevertheless, these shallow minima correspond to overall unfavorable interactions.

A Free energy simulations

B Unbiased simulations

FIGURE 4 | (A) Free energy profiles as a function of the center-of-mass distance between two R₉ or K₉ peptides obtained from AWH simulations (left). The average number of side-chain contacts between the peptides (as sampled during one set of AWH simulations with a looser criterion for exiting the exploration phase, see Section 2), presented along with the corresponding standard deviation (right). Two ionic conditions were tested: aqueous solutions containing only chloride counterions and aqueous solutions with 150 mM NaCl and 100 mM CaCl₂. (B) Radial distribution functions for C_z-C_z (in Gdm⁺ groups, top) and N_z-N_z (in NH₄⁺ groups, bottom) calculated from unbiased MD simulations of R₉ or K₉ in various aqueous solutions. Note that intramolecular interactions within a single peptide are excluded from these RDFs. AWH, accelerated weight histogram; MD, molecular dynamics; RDF, radial distribution function.

In contrast, K_9 peptides do not form any favorable binding configurations under any of the conditions examined. We also evaluated the average number of side-chain contacts between the two peptides in these AWH simulations. Specifically, we counted the number of C_z-C_z or N_z-N_z interactions within a 6 Å cutoff. Our results show that the energy minima for R_9 - R_9 arise from multiple favorable contacts between the like-charged side-chain groups, which is not the case for K_9 peptides.

Next, we performed unbiased MD simulations at two different peptide concentrations of 20 and 50 mM in aqueous solutions containing either counterions only or additional salt (NaCl or $CaCl_2$) at a concentration of 130 mM. The aggregation behavior of R_9 and K_9 peptides was analyzed using RDFs for the C_z-C_z (Gdm^+) and N_z-N_z (NH_4^+) atom pairs, respectively. As shown in Figure 4B, the RDFs (excluding intramolecular contacts of C_z-C_z and N_z-N_z) display distinctly different patterns for the two peptide solutions. The $g_{C_z-C_z}(r)$ functions exhibit sharp first peaks at a distance of approximately 0.39 nm across all studied systems, indicating significant interactions between Gdm^+ groups of arginine residues in different R_9 molecules. Notably, the interactions between Gdm^+ groups are enhanced by either increasing ionic strength or peptide concentration, similar to our observations in the AWH simulations. In contrast, the $g_{N_z-N_z}(r)$ functions do not show any distinct peaks, suggesting a lack of attractive interactions between ammonium groups.

4 | Conclusions

In this work, we performed NMR titration experiments for aqueous solutions of $GdmCl$ and NH_4Cl , maintaining constant ionic strength by adding appropriate amounts of NaCl. For the first time, we experimentally quantified the strength of Gdm^+ - Gdm^+ like-charge ion pairing. In particular, the pairing strength is approximately $-0.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ in a solution with an ionic strength of 3 M. In contrast, no pairing was observed for NH_4^+ ions. Our experimental findings are in excellent agreement with predictions from MD simulations and are further corroborated by results from DFT calculations. Next, we performed cryo-EM experiments on nona-arginines and nona-lysines in aqueous solutions containing NaCl and $CaCl_2$. We conclusively demonstrated that R_9 peptides, unlike K_9 , aggregate in water. This finding was further corroborated by unbiased and free energy MD simulations of solvated peptides, where R_9 (but not K_9) exhibited a tendency for attractive interaction, especially under ionic conditions that more closely resemble biological environments. Overall, our combined use of NMR and cryo-EM techniques, alongside computational methods, reveals that Gdm^+ -containing species exhibit like-charge ion pairing. This finding underscores the distinct and counterintuitive pairing behavior of Gdm^+ ions, which is driven by their specific chemical properties due to a unique electronic structure and water solvation effects.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/records/17775423> and <https://zenodo.org/records/17775424>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.